

**21-22 April 2023
OA Book Usage
Data Exchange
and Use Guidelines
and Principles
Workshop
Proceedings**

Acknowledgement

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Christina Drummond designed this document, which reflects unattributed participant contributions in line with the Chatham House Rules agreed to at the event.

April 21-22 2023 Rulebook Workshop Proceedings

Day 1: Friday, 21 April 2023

Getting started: Clarifying participant perspectives

Participants began by sharing their motivations for attending and broadly defining what they'd like to see coming out of the workshop.

Motivations for Participation	Personal Objectives
<p><u>Knowledge gathering</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn more about data spaces, policy, and governance Better support advocacy through improved understanding Identify stakeholder values, including those on the margins Meet the people involved <p><u>Improve usage data</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in accessing data that matters to show value Consider how to better extract value from data <p><u>Rules and ethics</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore reasons for open and closed data Explore potential misuses of usage Discuss rules <p><u>Represent other bodies / efforts</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Represent historical project context Advocate for existing standard use (COUNTER) Support the work as a member of project governance 	<p><u>Functional – Understand the IDS Technical Build</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consolidate focus Understand process to winnow down options Methodology for developing an implementation plan Get the nice to haves out that might be lowest on the list, things we could deprioritize so we can say “yes, but not now.” Timetable for action <p><u>Governance – Consider Principles and Rules</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop consensus around principles for regulation Develop something to assuage risk for those without time for a workshop Principles and values need to be backed up by action – what that looks like in practice <p><u>Relational Trust</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bridge parties across Europe and Trans-Atlantic Build trust in this room Understand blockers – why there might not be trust: “the sticky wickets” <p><u>Communications</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elevator pitch to take to the community Need something to take to the community Develop shared understanding of the definitions Understand the data trust effort enough to distribute that knowledge <p><u>Practical</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid DUL project outcome from being technically too complicated Learn from the past Avoid building something that small players can't use.

Definitions

Throughout the event, participants noted terms will require clear definitions in documentation. Time was not available to discuss IDSA and COUNTER definitions, but the intent was noted to leverage other definitions as much as possible.

What terms must be defined in an OAEBUDT glossary?

stewardship
 data contributor
 owner
 contributor
 data consumer
 access book data
 user usage
 see appendix a counter
 publicly available
 data sovereignty
 control
 member

Terms defined by the IDSA	Terms defined by other efforts	Unique Terms for the OAEBUDT Community
Data Contributor / Data Provider	Usage Data	Publicly Available
Data Consumer	Global Usage	Rights
Data Access	Aggregated Usage	
Data Sovereignty	Book Usage	
Controls	Chapter Usage	

A glossary will be included in the OA Book Usage Data Trust Rulebook to define such terms and sources.

Complex issues on people’s minds

A discussion of the complex issues that may come up in conversation occurred, surfacing topics on participants minds that spanned ethical, economic, socio-cultural, technological, and political concerns.

Complex issues shared by participants:

<p>Economic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Defining value of participation and learning from the failure of DUL ● History of aggregators not providing data back – what’s the likelihood they will buy in ● Worry about competitive harms from participation ● Finances – OA usage data – have to pay for this infrastructure – can the OAEBU be financially sustainable ● Sustainability of the data trust and impact of data sharing on the players ● Dangers of benchmarking: What targets should be and then using them to choose between competitors ● Monopolization – may be competitive and human nature – e.g., commercial platform/lg publisher who sees advantages and capitalize / monopolize a subject area – can data be used in a way to push out smaller publishers/platforms, or drive down value to then acquire ● What if a private company acquires the data trust? ● Will publishers create multiple Data Trusts instead of the one? ● Will libraries have to pay to access usage stats that are now free? Can analytics be sustainable, or do we create new inequities down the road? ● Network effects – if some players don’t participate, what is the impact? Need enough participation to have value 	<p>Socio-cultural</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Not breaking the unique diversity of books ● Engagement and participation of small players in data trust – harder one is having them participate in the governance as this is far from their other job – having them participating in the governance long term when the data trust is running. May be too costly for humanities ● Competitive academic culture – how the data we create / govern is used. If we create something that’s used in a non-constructive way, our own demise ● Bringing context around quantitative data. ● Risk aversion – could stop engagement ● Education and uptake ● Sense of pushback against technical solutions that appear they are general but coming from the journal players. Scholarly community around books – which could be skeptical if not included ● Smaller presses being not able to participate and the impacts that would have ● Journals are somewhat a monopoly in many spaces – if journals participate in this data space, they could overwhelm the book players ● Politics – right now going geographic, China, Central S. America – the voices of those on the margins, smaller, not part of the global north – what if they don’t want to participate in it?
<p>Technological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interoperability: tech, legal, policy ● What is a book – continuously evolves ● Challenge of usability vs. exact language – how to balance it: Rulebook must be lightweight, accessible, detailed ● Interacting in the supply chain if you’re not fully OA ● Building something that reinforces what we have, instead of creating something better 	<p>Ethical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If people use it in a poor way – out of context, or in a way that causes harm ● Unintended consequences ● Metrics – handle with care – risks of humans using them. Certainty of misuse ● Has to be a willingness to enforce the rules ● Dangers of quantitative usage data use – just because something is downloaded a lot it still generates rewards (P&T, etc.), how do you balance the benefits of showing that while not managing context

Session: Exploring Collective Usage Data Stewardship: Benefits and Trust

After an overview of aggregated pre-event participant survey results, participants discussed the value of having an “International Data Space (IDS) for OA book usage data exchange prior to discussing what kinds of activities would be harmful and what types of trust would be necessary.

What is the value of having a data space for OAEBU

<p>Infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Piece of the scholarly communications ecosystem that helps us solve global challenges” • Increase diversity of ecosystem • Demonstrate that this is possible • Values of standardization and interoperability for those would otherwise couldn’t contribute <p>Governance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Organize the discussion of the governance and make sure there is a political discussion of governing instead of having data sharing among themselves without” 	<p>Holistic Context - Seeing Data within a Bigger Picture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Completing the usage data picture so that I see the context beyond one org.” • Holistic picture of usage – publishers, authors can see – new avenues for players to see data, “Takes a village to see full picture” <p>Return on Investment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “There is a cost to contribute – but it is likely to support the sustainability of publishers.” • “Book publishing could benefit with innovation and growth” • “Make more effective, efficient use of resources” • “Creating possibilities to make informed decisions at all levels” • Improved Author Care / Customer Service: “any size publisher gets reports from everywhere – making it digestible for authors is impossible right now. “untangling information” 	<p>Usage and impact metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Coming out of smaller academic publishing, as authors chase higher impact journals – don’t want to encourage chasing factors for books but instead make something that can make us think differently about usage data and its importance. Still chasing big numbers, but maybe we can do something different than the impact factor regime.” • “Usage is a missing measure of impact – if we don’t aggregate it, we see less of the full picture” • “Fear of tyranny of metrics = if we don’t provide reliable metrics, someone will provide other metrics. Good metrics – reliable and trusted.”
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Challenges to Trust

Participants explored potential ways that participation in a Data Trust ecosystem could have unintended negative consequences and what could be done to address such issues. Potential solutions and open questions were noted.

Potential Harms	Potential Solutions	Open Questions
<p><u>Gaming the system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inflating numbers ● deliberately not sharing - selective data sharing ● deliberately putting in false data ● manipulation of the license ● Inappropriate access ● hacking into system ● sharing data access with non-members <p><u>Harm to data contributors:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● large publishers poaching authors based on usage ● release of data that exceeds rights ● Disclosure of restricted data <p><u>Harm to individuals:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify individual user/reader to put at risk ● Misuse of metrics to evaluate quality ● Inappropriately sharing protected info on readers, publishers, libraries ● Book censorship ● Author harm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define principles of acceptable use in Acceptable Use Policies (i.e., Usage Policies) ● Provide unacceptable examples ● Define benefits and value of controlled / restricted access ● Allow principles / policy terms to evolve (i.e., direct regulations) ● Allow for regular, scheduled revisions through a formal mechanism ● Expulsion from the OAEBUDT ● Legal liability ● Censure / financial freezing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Will we accept all data? ● How to support or address embargo problems

Session: Exploring Data Stewardship through the Data Trust

Small groups discussed what could be provided by the Data Trust to foster trusted data exchange. Ideation generated wide-ranging topics. Items in **bold** had small group consensus among the 3-5 seated at a table.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Shared understanding / definition of terms * ● Clear policies - i.e., with no ambiguity and minimal “wriggle-room” - on: * <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ aggregation level of data ○ data use and reuse ○ remedies for policy violation ○ definition of minimal acceptable data from contributors ○ whether data can selectively be omitted (e.g., excluding titles or underperforming data sets) ○ variation for different stakeholders ● Contributed data owned by data generator * ● Available to original publisher without limitation on reuse (dream state) ● Liberal license terms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ different variants may be needed? ○ open as possible but as closed as necessary ● Remedies for misuse ● Should we strip out PII: no personal data to engender trust? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Independent stewardship, non-aligned with any particular publisher or entity* ● Shared level of agreed upon metrics ● Shared understanding of results ● Shared understanding of how distributed ● POSI ● Ability to retain/control ownership ● CC-licenses for data ● Persistent identifiers ● Easy to input data into the OAEBUDT ● Liability for others using the data ● Open Access ● Trust in the process ● Agreement on funding 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal mechanisms ● Data sharing agreement ● Clear roles and responsibilities ● Permissions ● Appropriate security ● Privacy, incl. user privacy ● Clarity on what can be done with the data re: ownership / reuse ● Openness - commitment to maximize, reducing role of ownership ● Ownership - clarity - complexity, publisher/platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Global legal compliance* ● No further privatization of data - open data * ● Clear, inclusive regulation principles * ● Data producer = data owner??* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ implications of publishers-platform relationships; is there a right to use/access? ● Derived / derivative data must follow a ‘share-alike’ principle <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ if mixing private and open data?? ● ‘Pre-nup’ - allow access and withdrawal with clear processes (i.e., rules to develop trust) ● Rules for both the data and the organization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define risk: community defined (e.g., legal, financial) ● Define ownership ● license terms? types? ● would it allow removal of part of the data? ● individual vs. collective ● Low bar of entry ● for understanding ● to administratively assert ownership ● Address source of data ● Make governance transparent

Session: Exploring Data Reuse by Data Consumers

Small groups were asked to consider what was needed to guide the use and reuse of data transiting the data trust. Items in **bold** had small group consensus among the 3-5 seated at a table.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Follow/understand use cases* ● It's not viable/practical to monitor / handle reuse/violations* ● Have some role in responsible metrics* ● Have values and principles around reuse* ● Would reuse need to be controlled/monitored? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ by the DT ○ by data providers? ○ would it need to be possible for reuse violations to be reported / investigated / followed-up ● Reuse data policy, including follow up action ● Transparency best practices ● Education on use cases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clear guidelines on what I can / should do with the data* ● Unless necessary, aggregated data with no PII about people using the books* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ e.g., preliminary processing of data on-platform to aggregate e.g. geographic collection of usage before passing to OAEBUDT ○ define what is “necessary” ● Benchmarking where my books stand against competition* ● How to manage nefarious use <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How do we define this? ○ What remedies can we think of? ○ acceptable use focus (positive case) may be more useful ● Original publisher to have unrestricted of data from all sources of usage data for their published books ● Standard operating procedures ● What is an acceptable use policy? ● Is there a role for synthetic data? 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● “PIDs” for usage data set* ● CC license - citation attribution requirement for the usage data * ● Community of practice balance for adding to / benefiting from the OAEBUDT* ● Provenance through PIDs and metadata* ● with versioning ● Rules about reuse to detail compliance management (proactive and enforcement) * <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ongoing audits? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (Only) allow reuse if agreeing to principles* ● Transparency of the use of others data * ● Relicensed for commercial purpose * ● Stakeholder control via some kind of (open?) license ● Prevent noxious reuse by parties complying with principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data can't be withdrawn once submitted (+) * <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need a process to correct data ● simplicity of reuse - not too complex (+) ● allow data supplier to choose license (+) ● clear, enforceable parameters around re-use (+) ● ability to reuse/sort data for books I publish (-) ● As little friction as possible to reuse (+)

Session: Exploring Data Access by Data Consumers

Small groups were asked to consider what was needed to support or restrict the granting of data access via the data trust. Items in **bold** had small group consensus among the 3-5 seated at a table.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Well-documented access mechanism/API* ● Use & reuse rights clearly defined* ● Shared common language* ● Low friction to contribute and use* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ low technical barrier ○ low financial barrier ○ also legal, infrastructural, etc. ● Terms and conditions* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ who can do what, when, where, how and with which data ○ what happens if terms are breached ○ ?: is a CC-BY license viable, desirable, or sufficient ● Open/fair price for entry* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who defines fair? ● Level playing field (definition?) * ● Risk liability assessment ● for contributing data ● for using data ● Leverage the COUNTER-SUSHI API because libraries already use it and it is flexible enough to expand ● Could aggregate data be open but the details be restricted? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Appropriate access mechanisms for diverse users* ● Data configured to maximize useful open corpus (e.g. without PII, aggregates) * ● Low technical barrier of entry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ high accessibility ○ in what forms? reports, raw, etc.? ● Clear technical means for accessing data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ well defined APIs ○ stable mechanism ○ scalable/performant/cacheing ● Secure stability of access to data over time <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ e.g., via perpetual license ○ but need to be compatible with data regulations, e.g., Chinese firewall ● Compliance with POSI principles (legal entity) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Easy to extract data * ● Clear, simple methods of access* ● Equal stakeholder access to avoid competitive advantage ● Minimum reporting on what/who/how much access i.e., usage of the usage ● Platforms should only host open data (shared openly with a license) ● Not based on subscription payment (equal terms) ● Data needs to be publicly available (cc-license) or similar ● Open access to the data (open API) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standards for exchange and comparing of info* ● Policies and rules regarding data redistribution and reuse* ● Equal level of access for everyone* ● Make multiple formats of access available* ● Make the trust accessible* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reciprocity not mandatory* ● Annotation and provenance of usage data* ● Clear context, e.g., access to my own raw data but APIs for all data*; Clarify when talking about OA usage data vs. OA books* ● Clarity on access processes (what's is needed, how it is expected) * ● Different access levels and forms of membership* ● Approved data use policies* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ rule = no misuse of data ○ definition of misuse(?) ○ have enough resources to manage

First pass – practicing rule-development

At the conclusion of the first day of the workshop, a series of initial rules were brought forward for consideration based on these initial discussions. They were iterated live in the full group, with individuals indicating their level of support for statements as they were amended.

#1 re: Reporting of suspicious behavior
 Resulting Language: A mechanism will be available to report suspected usage data inconsistency.

If someone contributes inflated usage data, there will be a disciplinary hearing to investigate

A reporting mechanism will be available to report suspected usage data manipulation

A mechanism will be available to report suspected usage data inconsistency

#2 re: Action taken if merited
 Resulting Language: If evidence is found that data was inflated, the party will be asked to fix the data and/or be held accountable through a spectrum of accountability

If evidence is found that data was inflated, the party will be held accountable through a spectrum of accountability

If evidence is found that data was inflated, the party will be asked to fix the data and/or held accountable through a spectrum of accountability

#3 re: Range of accountability measures
 Full consensus on language not reached.
 Points made during discussion:

- Public notification could damage reputation.
- OAEBUDT-wide notification could say: a) data was updated, b) data was wrong and has been updated, or c) data was wrong because of Y and has been updated.
- Could give notifications a rating by provider.
- Need a way to know if a notification happened or not.
- Could explore a badge to reflect data accuracy - e.g., every time a mistake happens, reliability rating goes down.
- All terms would need to be defined: blacklisting, expulsion, etc.

Spectrum of accountability for clearly violating OAEBUDT rules will range from notification or warning to expulsion, blacklisting, or legal action

#4 re: OAEBUDT operational independence
 Resulting Language: The OAEBUDT will be independently governed, i.e., not wholly reliant on any one data provider or data consumer.

Points made during discussion:

- This may be difficult given key infrastructure and fiscal sponsorship partnerships

The OAEBUDT must be independently governed i.e. not aligned with any particular publisher or organization.

The OAEBUDT must be independently governed i.e. not reliant on any particular data provider or data consumer

The OAEBUDT will be independently governed i.e. not wholly reliant on any one data provider or data consumer

#5 re: Sharing of aggregated usage data

Full consensus on language not reached. The facilitator suggested changes did not address concerns. More work is needed.

Points made during discussion:

- To protect against harm, there has to be a retraction mechanisms.
- Not all data can be published openly.
- We need to define what "aggregate usage data" is specifically.
- Transparent algorithm and specific cases. Think we could then support. (+2)
- Third proposal is about OAEBUDT participation benefits, which differs from the first two on open licenses.

Day 1 concluded with a group dinner and an overview of the next day's agenda. The Executive Director reviewed outputs from Day 1, extracting the initial areas of small group consensus for rule-based discussion on Day 2. The topics and initial areas of consensus for further rule discussion included:

1. **OAEBUDT Participation as Data Contributor:** What types of organizations, and organizational requirements, must exist for an organization to contribute data through the OAEBUDT?:
 - a. To be an OAEBUDT data contributor, an organization must be the first party to create the data
 - b. Data consumers are not required to be data contributors.
 - c. Data consumers may have different levels of data access based on...
2. **OAEBUDT Data Ingest Requirements:** What if any requirements should exist for OA book usage data being exchanged to ensure that the data is trusted by data consumers?
 - a. To be ingested into the OAEBUDT, usage data must:
 - i. Include PIDs for if they are available
3. **OAEBUDT Participation as Data Consumer:** Are there any limitations on who can benefit from or access data exchanged or created by the OAEBUDT?
 - a. As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT will provide any data consumer to access the information.
 - b. Any data consumer can use the OAEBUDT to access data according to a pre-established contract negotiated out of the OAEBUDT
4. **OAEBUDT Data Use and Reuse Guidelines:** Exploring and defining any rules to define and encourage acceptable use and address inappropriate use
 - a. Use of Usage data accessed through the OAEBUDT is restricted as follows...
 - b. OAEBUDT data cannot be relicensed for commercial purposes
5. **Data Trust Operational and Participant Accountability:** To define requirements to ensure accountability by all engaging in the system to ensure trust in the Data Trust's core data exchange and processing processes
 - a. Data Consumer access of OAEBU data via the OAEBUDT will be logged and communicated back to the Data Contributor
6. **Data ownership** for exchanged and newly created OA book usage data
 - a. OAEBUDT data creators will retain individual ownership rights of raw or truncated usage data they contribute
 - b. New usage metrics processed and created by the OAEBUDT (e.g. aggregated totals, benchmarked totals) will be accessible to all OAEBUDT data consumers
 - c. Data accessed via the OAEBUDT will not be separately licensed or privatized.

Day 2: Saturday, 22 April 2023

The topics and initial prompts that surfaced in Day 1 were shared for further development in small group stations. Participants chose a station to begin at and then rotated throughout, with the objective of developing rules that could be brought to the full group for consensus-voting.

Original prompts reflected below in italics, with feedback recorded on notes in quotes above the revised, amended statements.

Station 1: Who can contribute data to the OAEBUDT

To be an OAEBUDT data contributor, an organization must be the first party to create the data

- “Remove ‘create’, must have right to provide!”
- “Authority to provide”
- “Any data provider must have authority to create and provide usage data to OAEBUDT”
- “Data contributors take responsibility for the data they provide”
- “...as stated in the bylaws/membership agreement (for the OAEBUDT)”
- “Data contributor should have legal rights to share the data”
- “To be an OAEBUDT Data Contributor, an organization must have the legal rights to contribute”

Amended statement: To be an OAEBUDT data contributor, an organization must have the right to provide the data.

Data consumers are not required to be data contributors.

- “Data providers may be data consumers”
- “Data provider, not data contributor”
- “global publishers, eBook platforms, libraries”
- steward

Data consumers may have different levels of data access based on...

- Crossed out - no alternative suggested

Suggested new statement: Data contributors must take responsibility for the data they provide.

Three rule statements related to Data Contributors were presented; consensus was reached on data providers having authority over and responsibility for the data they provide. Consensus also supported the notion that OAEBUDT Data Consumers do not have to be Data Contributors

Data Contributor Proposed Rule #1:

To be an OAEBUDT Data Contributor an organization must have the right to provide the data.

Feedback and suggestions provided during discussion include:

- How are we defining “the right”
- Replace ‘right’ with ‘authority’ (+3)
- Why say “Data Contributor” rather than “Data Provider”?
- Data contributor types must be defined, e.g. publisher, platform, etc.

Resulting Language:

To be an OAEBUDT Data Contributor an organization must have the authority to provide the data.

WHO1/3: To be an OAEBUDT Data Contributor an organization must have the right to provide the data.

Mentimeter

Data Contributor Proposed Rule #2:

Data Contributors must take responsibility for the data they provide.

Consensus reached with initial language.

Feedback and suggestions provided during discussion include:

- More information on what “take responsibility” means could be useful.

WHO2/3: Data Contributors must take responsibility for the data they provide.

Data Contributor Proposed Rule #3:

Data Consumers are not required to be Data Contributors

Consensus reached with initial language.

WHO3/3: Data consumers are not required to be data contributors.

Mentimeter

Station 2: How Is Exchanged Data Stewarded by the OAEBUDT

- OAEBUDT data creators will retain individual ownership rights of raw or truncated usage data
- New usage metrics processed and created by the OAEBUDT (e.g. aggregated totals, benchmarked totals) will be accessible to all OAEBUDT data consumers
- Data accessed via the OAEBUDT will not be separately licensed or privatized.
- OAEBUDT data providers will retain individual control of raw or truncated usage data
 - “Need clear definition of “control”
 - “Is control’ used to account for CC-0 licenses?”
- New usage metrics processed and created by the OAEBUDT will be made accessible
 - Suggestion to insert ‘publicly available’, “based on publicly available data” and “made publicly accessible”
- “What is publicly available data in this context and who is it accessible to (members vs. everyone)
- “Keep to all OAEBUDT consumers as we only speak about aggregated or benchmark totals”
- Data accessed via the OAEBUDT will not be separately licensed or privatized
 - “I don’t know what this means”
 - “Add ‘Original’ or ‘contributed’ to clarify”
 - “Have a clear ownership rule”

Two rule statements related to data stewardship in the Data Trust were presented; however, consensus was only reached on data providers retaining control over the data they contribute.

DataStewardship Proposed Rule #1:
 Data Providers will retain control of, and responsibility for, the data they provide.
 Consensus reached with initial language.
 Feedback and suggestions provided during discussion include:

- How is “controlled” defined?
- “Responsibility” needs to be defined too.

DATA STEWARDSHIP1/2: Data Providers will retain control of, and responsibility for, the data they provide.

Data Stewardship Proposed Rule #2:
 New governance-approved usage metrics, processed and created by the OAEBUDT, will be publicly accessible to all
 Full consensus on language not reached.
 More work needed.

DATA STEWARDSHIP2/2: New governance-approved usage metrics, processed and created by the DT, will be publicly accessible to all.

- Points made during discussion:
- Focus on interoperability, avoid “new” metric types being created outside of COUNTER
 - “Public accessibility to all” was a concern many as it was “too broad” a term, and could limit OAEBUDT participation benefits, thereby impacting long-term sustainability. A participant noted that OAEBUDT ownership of data must be explored.
 - Definitions and more information needed for terms including “governance”, “new”, and “publicly accessible”

Station 3: OAEBUDT Data Ingest Requirements

- To be ingested into the OAEBUDT, usage data must:
- Include PIDs for ... if they are available
- “Data has to be about OA books and chapters”
- “Could change in the future”
- “Must be trustworthy, actual, complete, and accurate”
- “‘trustworthy’ seems vague”
- “Must be clear on provenance, ownership, and licensing”
- “Stewardship”
- “Follow mutually agreed upon schema”
 - “minimal”
 - “optional”
 - “Replace ‘mutually agreed’ with ‘interoperable’”

Five rule statements related to data ingest into the Data Trust were developed and presented; however, consensus was only reached on an initial OA book and chapter usage and that rules should be followed.

Usage Data Quality: Proposed Rule #1
 Data provided to the OAEBUDT must be actual, accurate and complete.

Consensus not reached. More work needed.
 Points made during discussion:

- Need to define “actual, accurate, and complete”
- Exceptions may be needed
- One suggested “as complete as possible”, while another suggested “strict and clear”
- Concern over whether this rule could be used to subjectively allow or deny Data Trust participation
- One noted that you cannot force a data provider to contribute all of their data – that they should be able to choose what they upload.

WHAT: Data provided to the OAEBUDT must be actual, accurate and complete.

Usage Data Quality: Proposed Rule #2
 Data provided to the OAEBUDT should follow the principles of FAIR and CARE

Consensus not reached. More work needed.
 Points made during discussion:

- Does this mean the org subscribes to FAIR and CARE or the usage data provided is FAIR and CARE?
- How is this enforceable, not just checking a box? (And what would enforcement mean)
- How does an org show compliance
- Smaller presses may find this difficult
- What if usage data can't be provided in this format yet? Can they participate and strive to be better.
- Can't use the term “should” in a rule

WHAT: Data provided to the OAEBUDT should follow the principles of FAIR and CARE

Usage Data Quality: Proposed Rule #3

Data provided to the OAEBUDT will initially be about OA books and chapters based on agreed upon definitions
 Consensus reached with initial language.

Points made during discussion:

- Being open to opportunities to partner (e.g. GRASPOS)

WHAT: Data provided to the OAEBUDT will initially be about OA books and chapters based on agreed upon definitions

Usage Data Quality: Proposed Rule #4

OAEBUDT members will follow mutually agreed upon rules on provenance, ownership, and licensing.
 Consensus reached with initial language and minor edits.

Points made during discussion:

- Some wanted to focus on stewardship instead of ownership, others noted usage data ownership is important to know who owns the IP.
- Providing a range of licenses was proposed.
- How to implement “Mutually agreed” was unclear to one, as it suggested a conversation based approach instead of rules. One suggested omitting the term “mutually”
- Suggest focusing on “community standards”.

WHAT: OAEBUDT members will follow mutually agreed upon rules on provenance, ownership, and licensing.

Usage Data Quality: Proposed Rule #5

OAEBUDT members will follow agreed and interoperable metadata schema with minimal essential and optional optimum requirements.

Consensus not reached. More work needed.

Points made during discussion:

- Hard to understand
- Horrible language.
- Need to read thrice to understand.
- Need to clarify.

WHAT: OAEBUDT members will follow agreed and interoperable metadata schema with minimal essential and optional optimum requirements

Station 4: OAEBUDT DATA USE/REUSE

Use of Usage data accessed through the OAEBUDT is restricted as follows...

- “There has to be an acceptable range of licenses”
- “Has to do with what the licensee choses to share”
- “That is acceptable to the trust with a minimum... of openness”

Amended statement: Use of usage data accessed through the OAEBUDT is restricted according to the license terms assigned by the data provider

OAEBUDT data cannot be relicensed for commercial purposes

- “Is this data that is aggregated or remixed by the data trust”
- “Depends on the license”
- “Use of aggregated data as defined by OAEBUDT is not restricted”
- OAEBUDT data is divided into aggregated public data and granular private data”
- “What is granular/ private data is it the raw data from the data provider”
- “Reuse license for OAEBUDT members or all?”
- “Have direct access to the data or through a web-service?”

Amended statement: Data generated by OAEBUDT can

be relicensed for commercial purposes.

Three rule statements related to the use and reuse of data accessed via the OAEBUDT were presented; however, consensus was not reached. **Further discussion is required to define model data use licenses for a) data exchanged via the OAEBUDT vs. b) new data created by the OAEBUDT.**

Data Use and Reuse Proposed Rule #1: Use of usage data accessed via the OAEBUDT is restricted according to the model license terms chosen by the data provider.

USE/REUSE1/3: Use of usage data accessed via the OAEBUDT is restricted according to the model license terms chosen by the data provider.

Full consensus on language not reached.
 More work needed.

Points made during discussion:

- The details matter - want to review model licenses before voting.
- What if usage data is copyrighted or proprietary?
- Work needs to be done to determine a set of licenses with a range of terms as approved by the OAEBUDT governance/community
- A minimum standard of openness should be defined in said licenses

Data Use and Reuse Proposed Rule #2:
 Usage data provided to OAEBUDT can be relicensed for commercial purposes only as specified in the model license

USE/REUSE2/3: Usage data provided to OAEBUDT can be relicensed for commercial purposes only as specified in the model license.

Points made during discussion include:

- Need to clarify if this is for calculated data generated by the DT, not the raw data exchanged

While consensus reached, need "model" licenses and more work to affirm direction

Data Use and Reuse Proposed Rule #3:
 Aggregated and analytical data generated by OAEBUDT can be relicensed for commercial purposes by its members.
 Consensus on language not reached. More work needed.

USE/REUSE3/3: Aggregated and analytical data generated by OAEBUDT can be relicensed for commercial purposes by its members.

Points made during discussion:

- Provided the OAEBUDT is the data owner with the rights to use the derivative data, this could be okay
- Details about membership are needed to fully understand the implications of this statement. Questions included: "who are members", "why members" and "why not make this publicly accessible"
- The term "relicensed" needs to be scoped and defined
- Is "relicensing" a potential revenue stream

Station 5: How data is managed

Data consumer access of OAEBU data via the OAEBUDT will be logged and communicated back to the data provider

Note: one of the participants decided to start from scratch, generating a new list of statements which were then discussed in rotation:

- OAEBUDT will keep an audit log tracking activity by data providers and data consumers through the data trust
- “Any processing of data should be transparent”
- “There should be a clear ownership of the aggregate data set”
- “Data not stored?”
- No personally identifiable information will be kept in the audit log (only organizational information)
- “Data including personal info should not be uploaded/shared”
- Data providers can access audit logs for the data they have provided
- OAEBUDT management / governance have access to all audit logs
- “Clear description of the management, incl. contact details”
- Data consumers can access audit logs for their own activity
- Audit logs will be kept for 5 years
- “Why 5 years?”
- “5 years is a lot of data to keep”

Five rule statements related to how the OAEBUDT should operate to reinforce trust; consensus developed around the need for an audit log to track activity within the data trust, and the need to share such audit log records with OAEBUDT management and governance, data providers, and data consumers. Specific details on the form and nature of the audit logs must be developed and communicated given concerns over balancing privacy, security, and accountability.

Operational and Participant Accountability Proposed Rule 1:
 OAEBUDT will keep an audit log tracking organizational activity by data providers and data consumers through the DT

Consensus reached, but language is circular
 Points made during discussion:

- The OAEBUDT process will have to comply with GDPR requirements and IDSA standards
- “through the DT” is redundant

Suggested amended language: OAEBUDT will keep an audit log to track activity by data providers and data consumers within the Data Trust environment

HOW: OAEBUDT will keep an audit log tracking organizational activity by data providers and data consumers through the DT

Mentimeter

Operational and Participant Accountability Proposed Rule 2:
 OAEBUDT Data Providers can access audit logs for the data they have provided to OAEBUDT
 Consensus reached, no discussion

HOW: Data providers can access audit logs for the data they have provided to OAEBUDT

Operational and Participant Accountability Proposed Rule 3:
 OAEBUDT Data Consumers can access audit logs for their own activity

HOW: Data consumers can access audit logs for their own activity

Consensus on language almost reached. More work needed.

Points made during discussion:

- Disagreement over whether full IP addresses had to be logged for accountability.
- One noted that such logs may require sharing PII
- Anonymized audit logs were suggested, but their utility for accountability and cybersecurity investigations was questioned.
- SUSHI's use of an API token was noted, given the potential for that key to be logged so you know who had accessed the data on a given date/time...

Operational and Participant Accountability Proposed Rule 4:
 OAEBUDT management and governance have access to all audit logs

HOW: OAEBUDT management/governance have access to all audit logs

Consensus reached, no discussion.

Operational and Participant Accountability Proposed Rule 5:
 So there is no GDPR risk, no PII will be kept in the OAEBUDT audit logs

HOW: So there is no GDPR risk, no PII will be kept in the OAEBUDT audit logs

Consensus on language was not reached. More work is needed. It is unclear if the small group rationale for no PII was tied to privacy concerns and risk associated with full IP addresses associated with book or title usage OR if the concerns were tied to being held accountable for how the data would be used– i.e. tracking what is done with access to the data for cybersecurity and policy compliance. Varied responses made it clear that legal and data regulation experts must be involved in this area of rule-making.

Points made during discussion:

- Concerns varied over GDPR compliance, cybersecurity, accountability measures and privacy.
- Some wanted to make sure no PII was kept while others noted that IP addresses were needed to hold parties responsible and accountable for their actions in the data trust. "Can there be accountability if you cannot check who accessed the data" "I don't understand how you can have an audit log without IP addresses."
- Language could be broader than GDPR to reflect global legal compliance
- The importance of logging access to data in the trust by non members was noted

Data Consumer Participation

Note: Given the clarity of the suggestions coming out of Day 1, a small group was not formed. Two statements emerged for further community consultation:

- As a neutral data intermediary, the OAEBUDT will provide any data consumer to access the information.
- Any data consumer can use the OAEBUDT to access data according to a pre-established contract negotiated out of the OAEBUDT

Governance

The Board Chair and Board Secretary for the OA Book Usage Data Trust's Board of Trustees, i.e. the data trust's acting community governing body, shared current governing principles and draft by-laws with the group assembled. Due to time constraints, they invited feedback after the event.

Next Steps

C.Drummond, reiterated that the outcomes of the workshop would be documented and then built upon through community consultation during 2023.

Special thanks are due to the workshop participants who spent their weekend on this work.

Participants: Jo Lambert, John Lenahan, Jon Elwell, Björn Johansson, Niels Stern, Andrew Joseph, James Watson, Vivian Berghahn, Pierre Mounier, Cameron Neylon, Peter Potter, Ursula Rabar, Dimitris Pierrakos, Jennifer Kemp, Tasha Mellins-Cohen, Sharla Lair, Brian O'Leary, Sofie Wennström, and Johan Rooryck.

Facilitator: Barbara Grant

Project Investigators: Christina Drummond, Yannick Legré, Prodromos Tsiavos

Areas where additional rule-development is needed:

The following topics surfaced during the workshop as meriting focused attention outside of this event.

- **OAEBU Data Trust Membership:** What does it mean to participate in the Data Trust's IDS environment? Can the public pull down information or do they need to agree to abide by the terms and conditions of data trust participation in order to access the data? Such terms need to be considered and defined.
- **Accountability measures:**
 - Accountability related to usage data quality and consistency was discussed, however no rules related to adherence to OAEBUDT participation terms or data sharing and use agreements were discussed.
 - While a spectrum of accountability was discussed for trusted usage data, further work is needed to identify what measures and escalation processes are appropriate under which situations.
- **OAEBUDT generated data licensing:** Further discussion is needed to explore accessibility, licensing, and ownership of derivative data generated through OAEBUDT processing across all data contributors. e.g., Aggregated data APIs, Benchmark data APIs. Issues to balance include accessibility and OAEBUDT participant diversity, open infrastructure sustainability, and impacts on sustainability and membership models.
- **Licenses for Data Exchange via the OAEBUDT:** During the workshop attendees found it difficult to discuss potential rules for the downstream use of unprocessed data exchanged via the OAEBUDT, without access to model data sharing and use agreements (i.e., licenses) that support the data sovereignty principle core to the IDS model. Given the IDS recommendation that standard data sharing and use agreements (licenses) be deployed across all Data Consumers without prejudice, further stakeholder engagement is necessary to determine which terms would be acceptable for a viable OAEBUDT community.